

Neighborhood contextual merging of segments for landform detection and classification

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Abstract— Contextual merging of segments using spatial relations of the neighborhood and the geomorphometric variable of the neighbor segments is introduced as a method to improve the over-segmentation of object-based analysis. The scope of the approach is to provide better candidates for the detection and delineation of landforms with simple geomorphometric signatures like sinkholes and aeolian closed depressions. The approach is simple and effective and can be implemented in many GIS software. We exemplify it for the aeolian closed depression from a part of the Romanian Plain by using elevation standard deviation to merge the segments of such closed depressions. While generally, these can be considered as concave features; actually, these have multiple shapes: a flat bottom surrounded by concave, straight, and convex parts. The results are promising, but the approach needs to be better framed in a GUI GIS environment to be implemented for specific landforms detection and delineation tasks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Contextual spatial context is inherent in image classification and pattern recognition [1,2] and becomes essential in Object-based image analysis for remote sensing [3-5]. Contextual merging of segmentation results is a well-known approach in geomorphometry [6,7], although yet with limited applicability (pixel proximity and hierarchical clustering).

The present paper aims to assess the usability of the contextual merging of segments using the neighbors and their geomorphometric variables. The approach is considered useful because over-segmentation often happens when segments are obtained, and thus the geomorphometric signature is degraded. Or naturally, the shape is degraded by erosion or deposition. The method's main strength is the ability to use geomorphometrical data of the segments as criteria to decide the merge, compared to only shape, texture, or distance.

To exemplify the method's usability, we use the case of closed depressions of aeolian nature that, despite being seen as concave in shape, actually have multiple forms: a flat bottom surrounded by concave, straight, and convex parts while incised in the flat plateau. This was investigated already as a reality for concave and convex features like sinkholes and aeolian closed depressions (deflation depressions or blowouts) [8].

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Materials

The DEM used for testing the proposed approach is a Copernicus DEM (COP-DEM30) crop at 20 m resolution covering the Găvanu-Burdea Plain in Southern Romania (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. COPDEM at 30 m resolution for the study area.

B. Methods

While segmentation and polygon manipulation can be implemented in many software, I have used SAGA GIS [9] and R stat [10] because they are open source, and the reproducibility and readability is assured.

SAGA GIS watershed segmentation is a simple approach based on the ViGrA - Vision with Generic Algorithms (<http://hci.iwr.uni-heidelberg.de>) library [11] and is known to produce over-segmentation. Our objective here is different from dealing with these aspects here.

The *sf* package [12] representation of spatial geometry allows the integration with other R stat packages for straight manipulation of statistical methods and implementing machine learning algorithms. The spatial geometry analysis functions of *sf* package are also used for neighborhood identification and merging.

Figure 2. 3D view of the shaded surface and the segments of slope (x10).

The neighbors are found with *poly2nb* function (<https://r-spatial.github.io/spdep/reference/poly2nb.html>) and stored as a list of vector IDs.

The descriptive statistics of the geomorphometric variables (minimum, mean, maximum, range, variance, standard deviation, percentiles) for every segment are computed in SAGA GIS with the tool and stored as attributes in the segments file. Additionally, shape attributes could be computed and used if a certain shape is in the geomorphometric signature. I used only the descriptive statistics of altitude for the sample shown here. If the target landforms are influenced by various agents (water, air, ice), variables related to these agents could also be used (topographic wetness, drainage area, openness).

Polygons are read and stored as an attribute table with a geometry column ("*sf*" and "*data.frame*" class in R). IDs are assigned in a new column starting from 1 to n.

Every neighbor segment geomorphometric values are stored as table columns (1 to m, where m is the maximum number of neighbors), and indexes can also be computed.

The neighbor IDs list of vectors is filtered by the condition of geomorphometric variables, and only those fulfilling the condition will have the ID in the list. The rest of the IDs are set up to zero.

The neighbors that have IDs in the list will be merged with the *st_union* function (https://r-spatial.github.io/sf/reference/geos_combine.html).

Duplicated geometries are then removed, and all the polygons that intersect each other are combined. Another filter can be set up during the final union.

III. RESULTS

In Figures 3 to 5, I show a closed depression formed by the segment with ID 1605 and its seven neighbors. Using the mean, standard deviation elevation values of all the neighbors, the segments that have neighbors with values bigger than 1 m are merged. In the case of the closed depression shown in Figure 3, the merging is performed as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 3. Example of a polygon and its identified neighbors.

Figure 4. Example of a polygon merging with a single neighbor.

Figure 5. Example of a polygon merging with all the neighbors.

In Figure 6, I show a zoom 3D perspective view of the closed depression represented in Figures 3-5.

In the test, there was no further filtering based on geomorphometric variables. This would require the computation of the altitude statistics for the merged polygons. All the polygons that have intersections with other polygons are merged.

Figure 6. Example of the closed depression (segments with boundaries in red) formed by the polygon with ID 1605 and its seven neighbors.

IV. DISCUSSIONS

The OBIA (Object-Based Image Analysis) literature showed that objects (superpixels, segments) are better candidates for performing land-cover classifications. For DEMs, this should also be true [13].

In multiscale situations, the object delineation might need a scalar approach, but the process is straightforward for specific “simple” shapes.

The limitations of object-based approaches are given by the over- or under-segmentation, so assessing these aspects is needed when using segments for classifications. Our objective here is to avoid dealing with the algorithmic aspects of these issues. Instead, the focus is on the ability to contextually merge adjacent segments based on their geomorphometric variables regarding the neighbors.

The eCognition software has similar abilities to merge or grow neighbor segments. Still, it is limited to a single class and spectral values or segments shape characteristics (https://docs.ecognition.com/v9.5.0/eCognition_documentation/User%20Guide%20Developer/4%20Basic%20Rule%20Set%20Editing.htm). The algorithms implemented in eCognition are closer to the post-segmentation or semi-automatic/manual refinement.

Our approach is still straightforward in one iteration, but in this specific example can merge the segments of closed depressions pretty well. From this point on, new iterations can be used, or statistical models can be fitted to train a model for detecting and delineating closed depressions. The other merged features will need to be labeled in other classes.

Figure 7. The merged polygons (in red) after a first iteration for neighbors that have a mean, standard deviation of altitude bigger than 1.5 m.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The results are promising for the aeolian closed depression as a landform with a clear geomorphometric signature. For complex signatures, the complexity of the approach needs to be increased by adding iteration and other rules, but we are confident that this is achievable. The approach needs to be better framed in a GUI GIS environment to be implemented for specific landforms detection and delineation tasks.

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